

Character of Population Services in the Country Border Area in Talaud Islands Regency, North Sulawesi Province

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Abstract:- This study aims to identify and analyze the character of population services in the national border region in the Talaud archipelago district, North Sulawesi province, Indonesia. Using qualitative research methods, primary data sources and secondary data with interview data collection techniques, literature study, observation. Civil servant informants, NGOs, mass media, universities, tested the validity of the data by triangulating findings and data sources. Data analysis techniques are reduction, presentation, condensation and data verification. The character of the service has not found population administration regulations, there are no sub-district technical implementing unit offices, service standards are not implemented, the service is slow to respond and convoluted and there are still favoritism services. Practically, it is hoped that the results of this research can be useful for improving the quality of human life and must consider the urgency of the research carried out and can be felt in the short term or the benefits that will be felt in the future.

Keywords:- Character, Population Services, Country Border Area.

I. INTRODUCTION

Population administration is a series of structuring and controlling activities in the issuance of population documents and data through population registration, civil registration, and management of population administration information and the utilization of the results for public services for the development of other sectors (Rohman, 2013).

The concept of archipelagic character is seen from the specific character of the Talaud Archipelago Regency which is geographically located at coordinates 3° 38' 00" - 5° 33' 00" North Latitude (LU) and 126° 38' 00" - 127° 10' 00" East Longitude (BT). This district is included in the border area between countries because its geographical position is between Sulawesi Island (NKRI) and Mindanao Island (Philippines). (SKPT Talaud Ministry of Marine Affairs and Fisheries).

Above the territorial boundaries of the Talaud Archipelago Regency: to the north it borders the Republic of the Philippines; To the east it is bordered by the Pacific Ocean; To the south it is bordered by the Maluku Sea; In the west it is bordered by the Sangihe Islands Regency.

Administratively, the Talaud Islands Regency is included in the territory of North Sulawesi Province with Melonguane as the district capital which is 271 nautical miles from the capital of North Sulawesi Province (Manado). The Talaud Islands Regency has a total area of 39,051.02 Km² which consists of an area of 37,800 Km² of sea water (96.79 %) and a land area of 1,251.02 Km² (3.21%).

Administratively, the Talaud Islands Regency has 19 sub-districts, 11 sub-districts and 142 villages. North Beo District is the largest area with a land area of 144.85 Km² (11.58% of the land area of Talaud Islands Regency), while Miangas District is the smallest sub-district with a land area of 2.39 Km² (0.19% of total area) . mainland of the Talaud Islands Regency). The administrative area of Talaud Islands Regency is spread over 7 of the 17 islands.

Fig 1:- Map of the distance between the sub-districts of Miangas (Indonesia) and Marawi (Philippines) and public transportation modes

Population services between islands or with an archipelagic character are distinguished from non-archipelagic population services. If population services are archipelagic in character with remote geographical conditions, difficult to reach by public transportation, and access to public services is very limited, and population services can be provided in sub-districts, while non-archipelagic population services are held at the population and civil registration office (Disdukcapil) it is centralized . (Permendagri no. 120 of 2017)

Law Number 23 of 2006 states that a population document is an official document issued by an implementing agency that has legal force as authentic evidence resulting from population registration and civil registration services. Then population data are individual data and/or structured aggregate data as a result of population registration and civil registration activities. While population events are events experienced by residents that must be reported because they have an impact on the issuance or change of Family Cards, Identity Cards and/or other certificates of residence including moving in, change of address, and status of limited stay to permanent residence. Wyckoff (2006) quality of service is highly dependent on the ability of the government to fulfill the wishes of its people. The phenomenon of tangibles or physical appearance, namely the lack or lack of human resources at the Disdukcapil office . The number of employees in the Disdukcapil Talaud is 24 people, consisting of 10 men and 14 women.

According to Jiali Dai (2016) that in April 2012, the Guangdong Provincial government selected Huizhou City as the first pilot city to further promote comprehensive reforms on the basic equity of public services. But among basic public services, medical and health services are developing slowly and this is very unequal.

Table 1. Distance between the Capital of the Talaud Islands Regency and Miangas District to Several Cities in the Philippines

No	districts	Cities in the Philippines	Nautical Mile	km
1	Melonguane	Davao City	289	465.1
2	Melonguane	General Santos	219	352.446
3	Miangas	Cape St. Augustine	50.4	81,111

Source: Department of Transportation of the Talaud Islands Regency

Table 1. Miangas sub -district is an area directly adjacent to the Philippines, meaning that geographically the Miangas sub-district is closer to the neighboring Philippines than to the capital of the Talaud archipelago district, namely Melonguane. The fact that public services are very far can be seen in the Talaud Islands Regency, such as the Lirung sub-district which covers a distance of only 18,149 km to the capital of the Talaud Islands Regency, namely Melonguane , using sea transportation modes, namely speedboats with a duration of 30 minutes.

Population services that are very far away, such as the Essang sub-district, are 75 km from the capital of the Talaud archipelago district, namely Melonguane, but the distance is using land transportation because it is one island with the capital of the Talaud archipelago district, namely Karakelang island. The inter-island population service in the border area with the Philippines is a unique public service description because it has to pass through the sea and the brunt of the waves.

Fig 2. Map of the border between the Republic of Indonesia and the Philippines

Source: Google.com map

Population services in the form of an electronic ID card are still 5.22% of the population who have not recorded an e-KTP, this figure shows that it is not yet 100% when compared to other areas which on average have 100% recorded an e-KTP.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Graph 1. Development of e-KTP services in the Talaud . Islands Regency

Source: Office of Population and Civil Registration Office of the Talaud Islands Regency

Another fact found is that there is no regulation on population administration that regulates the signing of population documents by the Head of the UPT, there is no UPT Disdukcapil office building available in 5 (five) district , namely: a). Nanusa sub-district which is located on the island of Nanusa; b). Miangas sub-district, which is located on the island of Miangas, borders the Philippines; c). Kabaruan sub-district on Kabaruan island including Damau sub-district and Kabaruan sub-district; d). Salibabu sub-district on Salibabu island includes Lirung sub-district, Moronge sub-district, Salibabu sub-district and Kalongan sub-district; e). Gemeh sub-district on the island of Karakelang includes Melonguane sub-district, East Melonguane sub-district, Beo sub-district, North Beo sub-district, South Beo sub-district, Rainis sub-district, Tampan'Amma sub-district, Pulutan sub-district, Essang sub-district, South Essang sub-district and Gemeh sub-district . Posumah (2021).

Cases of residents who died but the data has not been deleted because a death certificate has not been issued, double data were found such as population mutations between villages within the sub-district and between sub-districts within the district where the data is not under the Disdukcapil for entry so that he is still registered in the previous village or sub-district, there are residents registered in village but not registered with Disdukcapil (source: rri.co.id 30/4/2017).

Law number 25 of 2009 concerning Public Services in article 5 paragraph 7 states that government administrative actions are required by the state and regulated in laws and regulations in order to realize the protection of personal, family, honor, dignity and property of citizens. For the people, ownership of ID cards and family cards is very much needed because they are used as a condition in accessing every other public service such as installing electricity, opening an account at a bank, civil registration services, managing passports, and others.

Collaboration between the public sector and social organizations has become a major trend in terms of public service delivery in China. To provide a systematic framework for better understanding the regional variations of local government purchasing public services from social organizations. Drawing on a comparative case study between Yunnan and Guangdong Province, it highlights how critical factors, such as the level of local economic development, environment, policy support and quality of social organization, influence government purchases of public services in these two areas. (Liheng Qi & Jia Guo, 2017).

Dwiyanto (2002) that a good service delivery system can be seen from the amount of human resources owned by the bureaucracy that are effectively utilized to serve the interests of service users. Ideally, all the capabilities and resources possessed by the bureaucratic apparatus are only devoted or concentrated to serve the needs and interests of the community. The dimensions of public service dimensions according to Zeithaml , Parasuraman & Berry (1990; 1991; 1993; 1996) they state that:

- Tangibles or physical appearance, means the physical appearance of buildings, employee equipment and other facilities owned by providers. The indicators are the appearance of the officers/apparatus in serving customers, the convenience of the place to perform the service, the ease in the service process, the discipline of the officers/apparatus in performing the service, the ease of access of customers in requesting services, and the use of assistive devices in the service.
- Reliability or reliability is the ability to carry out the promised service accurately. The indicator; Accuracy of officers in serving customers, Have clear service standards, Ability of officers / apparatus in using tools in the service process, Expertise of officers in using tools in the service process.
- Responsiveness or responsiveness is a willingness to help customers and provide services sincerely. The indicator; Respond to every customer/applicant who wants to get service, Officers/apparatus perform services quickly, Officers/apparatuses perform services appropriately, Officers/apparatuses perform services carefully, Officers/apparatuses provide services in a timely manner, and All customer complaints are responded to by officer.
- Assurance is the knowledge and courtesy of workers and their ability to give trust to customers. The indicator; Officers provide guarantees on time in service, officers provide guarantees for costs in service, officers provide guarantees of legality in services, and officers provide guarantees of cost certainty in services.
- Empathy is the treatment or personal attention given by providers to customers . the indicator; Putting the interests of the applicant/customer first, the officer serves with a friendly attitude, the officer serves with a polite attitude, the officer serves without discriminatory (discriminatory), and the officer serves and respects every customer. (Nurdin, 2019).

Service (Thoha, 1991) is devotion and protection, the administrator's task emphasizes putting the interests of the community before their own interests. Service can be defined as an activity provided to assist, prepare and manage either in the form of goods or services from one party to another (Donald 1984; Lovelock 1991; Poerwadarminta 1995). According to David McKeivitt (1998) that services are important for the protection and improvement of people's welfare. Limba (2013) the main problems faced in implementing electronic public services, best practices in European Union countries, regulations and perspectives on the development of electronic public services in Lithuania. Lewis & Gilman (2005) public service is public trust. Citizens hope that public services can serve with honesty and proper and accountable management of income sources to the public. Suparman (2016) that public services are still poor, this is indicated by the large amount of service discrimination, the absence of service certainty, the low level of community satisfaction and even services tend to be "commodities". Denhardt & Denhardt (2007) divide the paradigm of state administration into 3 paradigms, namely: OPA, NPM and NPS, they conclude that the most up-to-date paradigm in state administration is the New Public Service (NPS).

III. PAPER OBJECTIVE

This study aims to explain and analyze the character population service for the border area of the country in the Talaud archipelago district, North Sulawesi province.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The type of qualitative research is contextual research that uses humans as instruments and is adapted to a reasonable situation in relation to data collection which is generally qualitative in nature (Creswell, 2016). Primary data comes from informants in the form of information and data from interviews with people who incidentally are stakeholders and state civil servants in the Office of Population and Civil Registration of the Talaud Islands Regency Government. Literature studies are carried out by reviewing and studying reading materials of various books, internet, journals, scientific papers, documents, including various regulations and other reference materials deemed relevant to the object of research.

Triangulation of findings so that findings are not considered biased, researchers need to triangulate findings, or what is often referred to as confirmability, namely by reporting research findings to interviewed informants. Researchers choose which data is most relevant to be used to support research. Qualitative data can be obtained from interviews, observations and literature studies. Data analysis techniques are data reduction, data presentation, data condensation and data verification.

Fig 3. Interactive model data analysis (Miles & Huberman, 2014)

V. RESULTS

➤ Reliability

The results of the observations show that what the informants say is true, more freelance daily workers who are at the forefront of service at the counter are seen wearing black and white uniforms. There are 24 employees at the Population and Civil Registration Office and 17 freelance daily workers (THL), the condition of the existing employees according to service observations at the counter is more dominated by freelance daily workers. However, in reality the accuracy of the State Civil Apparatus (ASN)/employees in serving the community is still very weak, it can be seen that there are still many people who go back and forth every day to the Disdukcapil office to take care of their interests, be it your Resident Card, Family Card or birth certificate, death certificate, marriage certificate, etc.

According to Leny Nae as the Head of PIAK Disdukcapil, it was said that there were cases of several families who had lived for 20 years in the Talaud Islands Regency but their family cards were still registered in the Philippines, so the island district government Talaud is in a dilemma because the Immigration side requires a document to transfer citizens from the Philippines to Indonesia, but the discretion carried out by the Disdukcapil takes steps to process the document to issue a family card and ID card automatically has re-entered into an Indonesian citizen because the person concerned is originally a Talaud person. There is still a lack of human resources at the sub-district Disdukcapil UPT, the number of Disdukcapil employees is 20 people and database administrator employees are 4 people.

Sumber: Disdukcapil Talaud diolah peneliti

Fig 4. Standard service procedures

Standard operating procedures and service standards at the Disdukcapil office are available but not implemented properly, that is, they are not shown to the public as residents of population services.

➤ *Tangibles*

The results of observations are indeed still very low on existing services, one of the reasons is that the Office of Population and Civil Registration is the center for population services and serves the community from the existing 19 sub-districts, this is a logical consequence of service centralization. The facilities and infrastructure are not sufficient to provide population services that urgently need information and technology facilities and infrastructure as well as an internet-based service system. The phenomenon of the appearance of computers and laptops and inadequate internet networks will be an obstacle in population services in the Talaud archipelago district. Per the regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia number 120 of 2017 says that the local government through the Department of Population and Civil Registration of the Talaud Islands Regency has formed a Disdukcapil Technical Implementation Unit although it is only limited to 5 (five) UPT Disdukcapil offices including Nanusa sub-district, Miangas sub-district, Kabaruan sub-district, Salibabu sub-district and Gemeh sub-district. Then these five sub-districts are expected to be able to reach overall services, this shows that the implementation of the policy of Permendagri number 120 of 2017 article 11 concerning the formation of the Disdukcapil UPT in each sub-district has not been realized.

➤ *Responsiveness*

Observations show that many people still have to wait a long time for a service to be provided, because every working day only a few people are in the Disdukcapil office, which is different from population services in non-island areas where every working day many people take care of their population administration. That a lot of people then complained about the services of the Disdukcapil office and they mentioned that the office that was the slowest in responding to public complaints was the Disdukcapil Talaud office. This is due to the disappointment of the people who travel very long

distances and use boat transportation modes to arrive at the office location, then they are served with results that are not optimal. Finally, the community is spontaneously disappointed with the difficult service and does not respond quickly to the wishes and needs of the community.

The table below shows how far the distance traveled to take care of population services and have to use the sea transportation mode (speedboat) which is challenging with the swift waves and sea waves.

Table 2. Capital to District and Distance to District Capital by District in Talaud Islands Regency

No	Districts	District Capital	Distance to Regency Capital (km)
1	Kabaruan	Mangaran	22,224
2	Damau	Damau	40,559
3	Lirung	Lirung	18,149
4	Salibabu	Salibabu	25,928
5	Kalongan	Kalongan	16,668
6	Morongge	Morongge	27.78
7	Melonguane	Melonguane	-
8	Melonguane Timur	Bowombaru	12
9	Beo	Beo	35
10	Beo Utara	Lobbo	48
11	Beo Selatan	Tarohan	28
12	Rainis	Rainis	47
13	Tampan'Amma	Dapalan	75
14	Pulutan	Pulutan	49
15	Essang	Essang	75
16	Essang Selatan	Sambuara	49.5
17	Gemeh	Gemeh	94
18	Nanusa	Karatung	107.41
19	Miangas	Miangas	229,648

➤ *Empathy*

The phenomenon of empathy is one of the phenomena that must be considered by every Regional Work Unit in the government bureaucracy, especially at the Office of Population and Civil Registry of the Talaud Islands Regency to provide treatment or personal attention to the community in population services. Observations that there are indeed factors of proximity to employees have always been a scourge in public services, even though it seems that the services provided are polite and friendly. Public service seen from the empathy dimension, the level of willingness of the local government to know the wants and needs of the community is still lacking because the realization percentage of people who already have an ID card is only 90%, this shows that it is still far from the feasibility of public services that take place in the Talaud Islands district government.

The limited population services in the Talaud Archipelago Regency are based on territorial characteristics with archipelagic, cultural and economic characteristics. Even though the community benefits, it is difficult to observe the implementation of population services there, because the average level of education is not yet high, it can be seen from

the number of employees with S2 education as many as 1 person, employees with S1 education as many as 11 people, employees with high school education as many as 9 people. Despite the centralized character of the population service, the role of the observations is very strong.

VI. DISCUSSION

Klierová & Kútik (2017) Service quality significantly determines the quality of human resources involved in this system. The results of the synergy are cheaper, more efficient and easier public services and public administration. Public services and public administration should be cheaper, more efficient and more accessible to the public.

Shahda (2016) public service motivation (PSM) or public service ethos (PSE) is useful for improving the performance of public servants in America. PSM has been studied in various developing countries; but it is almost ignored in developing countries including Indonesia. In addition to time uncertainty, Hardiansyah (2018) cost uncertainty is a complaint of citizens when dealing with the bureaucracy, this is due to the absence of clear service standards within the framework of service operational standards to the cost consequences so as to bribe the bureaucratic apparatus for the smooth running of its affairs.

The service chaos is because all employees work to serve the community without standard operating procedures, so that people who come from various islands have difficulty taking care of population administration documents. How can the community find out the requirements needed to take care of population administration documents and where to start, then where are the affairs and where will they be completed and in how long the population administration affairs will be completed. One of the principles of service standards from Kepmenpan No. 63 of 2003 concerning general guidelines for the implementation of public services, namely the certainty of when the implementation of public services can be completed within a predetermined period of time, but expectations are not in accordance with reality. Supporting facilities such as computers, laptops and internet networks in each sub-district are not entirely adequate.

Responsiveness according to Lenvinne (1990) is to measure the responsiveness of service providers to the hopes, desires and aspirations and demands of the community. The dimension of responsiveness is still a lot of complaints from the public in connection with the population services provided which are still slow, inappropriate and not responded to optimally by employees. In order to get a quick, accurate and precise population service and all complaints from the community, it is rather difficult for employees to respond. Observations that the phenomenon of long service distances, such as Salibabu island to Karakelang island where the Disdukcapil office is domiciled, the journey duration is 20 minutes using motorboat transportation mode, wading through waves and large ocean currents causing nausea, but for those islanders who have been getting used to this kind of transportation is taken for granted.

Services according to Ivancevich, Lorenzi, Kinner and Crosby (1997) in (Ratminto and Winarsih, 2005) are products that are invisible (cannot be touched) that involve human efforts and use equipment. His article published in the business research journal Gronroos (1990) said that service is an activity or a series of activities that are invisible that occur as a result of interactions between consumers and employees or other things provided by service providers with the aim of solving consumer problems. /customer.

With the character of population services in the border areas of the country, it is rather difficult for researchers to match the traditional paradigm, considering the territorial typology with archipelagic character so that it is rather difficult to obtain optimal services holistically. Nevertheless, the population service for the border areas of the country is absolutely carried out with a service character in the Talaud archipelago district. National borders have 2 dimensions according to Law no. 43 of 2008 namely: 1). The boundary of the border region is the line limit which is separator sovereignty something country based on law international and 2). Border area is part from Territory of the country located on the side in along limit Indonesian territory with other countries. One of the priority activities for border areas is the development of underdeveloped areas, border areas, rural areas, and transmigration (Diantoro, 2020).

VII. CONCLUSION

Reliability or reliability of the character of population services will be optimal if the ability of the Population and Civil Registry Office of the Talaud Islands Regency in creating the promised population services correctly. However, the facts show that the services of ID cards, family cards, marriage certificates, birth certificates, death certificates are not optimal and the ability of the State Civil Apparatus or employees to serve both skills and knowledge is still not optimal and the actual Standard Operating Procedures must be posted in the Disdukcapil office. and implementation of service standards. Human resources are the main factor in moving an organization but in reality the ability of employees to operate computers as a service medium in providing population services is still low. The data obtained by mandatory ID cards of 75,559 people and mandatory ID cards that have not recorded 4484 people, this indicates that the remaining 5.60% of mandatory electronic ID cards have not recorded.

Tangibles or the physical appearance of the character of population services will run well according to the needs of the community if the local government has provided physical appearance, for example the sub-district Disdukcapil UPT building is not optimal because only 5 (five) Districts are available and not complete and human resources are available, then physical appearance the employees of the Disdukcapil office of the Talaud Islands Regency are very neat and elegant. However, the convenience of the community to easily get fast and hassle-free service is still far from the reality in population administration services. Although in terms of the physical appearance of employees, they are neat and elegant, the availability of equipment as a

means of supporting information and technology in the administration of population services is certainly not available in the 5 (five) sub-districts of the UPT Disdukcapil offices which have been determined by the Regent of the Talaud Islands Regency.

Responsiveness or responsiveness of the character of population services will be successful if employees can provide appropriate, accurate and precise services and the government bureaucratic organization of the population and civil registration office of the Talaud Islands Regency immediately responds to all complaints and wishes of the community. The reality on the ground indicates that population services are still slow and not timely so that all complaints from the community are slow to respond or respond to employees as community servants.

The empathy character of population services can be optimal if the Disdukcapil office employees can provide services by being friendly, full of courtesy and not being selective or selective in providing population services to the community. Although it is very good from the friendly attitude and courtesy of the employees as public servants, there are still employees who carry out their duties selectively or selectively to the community. Population services at the Disdukcapil office are still selective or selective based on family, friends, or other humanist affinities.

Practically, it is hoped that the results of this research can contribute to the Regional Government of North Sulawesi Province to be able to better understand the meaning and purpose of the population service model for the border areas of the State with archipelagic character or the outermost islands and develop various approaches that have been scientifically researched and tested. It is hoped that it will be useful for improving the quality of human life and should consider the urgency of the research carried out and can be felt in the short term or the benefits that will be felt in the future.

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